
Rice-based cropping systems

Relay cropping of Nendran banana in rice fields in Kerala, India

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Rice cultivation is becoming less profitable in Kerala because of rising costs of labor and inputs. Inflow from other Indian states has also depressed rice prices. Farmers are switching their better drained, terraced rice fields to cassava, sweet potato, Nendran banana (which belongs to the Horn-plantain group), and vegetables. A 2-year rotation of Nendran banana, cassava, and medium-duration rice is now common in terraced rice tracts. Other short-duration vegetable crops such as colocasia, sweet potato, cucumber, okra, or amaranthus are also grown between the banana plants, making it a 3- or 4-tiered cropping pattern. The growing of different crops with canopies of varying heights simultaneously on the same land optimizes exploitation of available solar energy.

But some farmers in the terraced rice fields of Malappuram district practice an unusual system – relay-cropping of rice and Nendran banana (see photo). Beside the usual single rice crop, a crop of Nendran banana is also raised yearly, bringing a net profit of about \$1,200/ha.

Nendran banana and rice in fields of Kerala, India.

After the onset of the southwest monsoon, the autumn rice crop is transplanted as usual. Once seedlings are established, fresh Nendran banana suckers with pseudostems 40 to 50 cm in height are thrust in the standing rice crop, spaced 2 m apart. The bananas receive no attention until harvest. Rice is cultivated as usual. By the time of rice harvest, each banana sucker has produced 3 or 4 small

leaves (on which birds perch to eat rice insect pests).

Stagnant water is drained after the rice harvest. The field is gradually converted into beds and furrows with spades, thus placing the banana suckers in beds that are gradually raised by applying green leaf manure and earth. The beds and furrows serve as both drainage channels in rainy months and as channels for furrow irrigation in summer.

After beds and furrows are formed, seeds of intercrops such as cucumber and okra are dibbled and colocasia corn is planted between banana suckers. A farmyard manure-ash mixture is usually applied in the bed for both the banana and intercrops; nitrogen and potassium fertilizer are sometimes applied. The banana suckers grow vigorously and begin to shoot about 7 months after planting. The crop is irrigated by furrows or furrows combined with splash irrigation. Each banana plant is propped for wind protection. The bunches mature 3–3.5 months after shooting. Some farmers claim that they harvest banana about 1 month earlier by using the system. This type of relay cropping is practiced only on alternate years in double-cropped rice fields. With moderate fertilizer application, the rice crop that succeeds the banana crop gives bumper yields. ■

CORRECTIONS

IRRN 3:5 (October 1978)

Page 7. In A.K. Roy, *Reaction of rice cultivars to rice sheath and leaf blight*, paragraph 1. line 9, should read: "Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in small plots (5 rows each), replicated twice."

Page 7. Paragraph 6. line 11, of A. K. Roy's article – Delete "Sikirimonko."

Page 22 – The legend *Plant ht (cm)* on the upper part of the figure should read *Root wt (g)*.

IRRN 3:6 (December 1978)

Page 12 – In the figure legend, ■ *Biotype 3* should read ■ *Biotypeshifting*.
